

Exploring The Relationship Between Transactional Leadership And Organizational Commitment: Mediating Role of Intrinsic Motivation

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 14, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: October 15, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Transactional Leadership, Intrinsic Motivation & Organizational Commitment</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7199521</p>	<p><i>The education enhances human abilities to play their role in making a conducive environment, which can preserve their social and secure. In this way, the basic tasks fall upon shoulders of concerned teachers who over their competencies, knowledge, skills and abilities can produce committed and motivated employees in diverse economic sectors. Along the same line, teachers themselves need leaders who can make them motivated and committed to their institutions. In this regard, the leadership is a challenging fact for researchers and academicians. Numerous researchers have focused on styles of leadership in varied professions, situations, backgrounds and cultures. This phenomenon was examined among teaching communities at the higher educational institutions at different levels. The study is expected to be unique in the sense that it has used motivation (intrinsic) as a mediator in linking the leadership styles (transactional) and organizational commitment that lack in existing research on issues under consideration. In this regard, the researcher used the main variables of study as global variables like leadership styles, commitment and motivation as per the hints from the existing research studies to make clear the contributions towards the existing database of knowledge regarding the issues under consideration.</i></p>

Introduction

Abdul and Fatimah (2015) described that leadership in academic institutions mark to process of managing teachers and pupils fruitfully to approach the goals related to education. Crispen, Michael and Mariri (2004) explained that leadership, during past decades, has been an area of far consideration and discussion and how diverse leadership styles kindle diverse feedback from employees. From the educational sector, group dynamics, and “leader and led” contribute much to the credibility of institutions. Nazirah, Kamal and Seri (2015) revealed that leadership in higher education is finding it difficult to keep motivation and commitment on the priority to obtain maximum productivity on the part of concerned employees keeping in view efforts and input toward respective institutions. Leadership starts with the qualities approach comprising the leaders’ behaviours deciding leadership sufficiency. One of speculations that get a charge out of the significance, improvement and constant research is the idea of transformational and transactional leadership. Qamar et al., (2016) asserted that according to situational, leaders are products of assumed situations and leadership is influenced by conditions from where leader raises and where they work.

Osabiya and Ikenga (2015) narrated that leadership over certain style motivate individuals, provides direction and implement plans and such style are imitated both in the behaviours but these are results of the diverse, compound and complicated interactions among manners we feel and think. There are manifold and various styles and approaches to management and leadership based on various theories and rules. The individuals using styles would be based upon beliefs, preferences and values, norms and organizational culture that would inspire some styles while others dismay others. This is obvious statement both right and wrong styles are there. Thus, leadership and commitment are considered the leading characteristics towards desired commitment. According to Irfan and Nawaz (2016), capable and effective leadership is a phenomenon to make these institutions at par with international standards. Irfan, Nawaz and Saqib (2013) stated that institutional standing and success depend upon the effectiveness of leadership in institutions. Likewise, the effectiveness of leadership is the effectiveness of the institution. The effectiveness of the institutions depends on some factors which are accountable for the effective functioning of academic institutions.

In this linking, among these dynamic factors, important most is phenomenon of organizational commitment. It is commitment which makes institutional workforces enthusiastic and inspired to perform committedly in the diverse situations. In this context, the incidentally, concerning organizational commitment, the role of leadership

style is phenomenal. Blazes (1978) pointed out that transformational leadership is the fast-grasped attention of the researchers. This opinion was rectified to accumulate a complete model of leadership. The related study focused on the objective to figure out major leadership styles in both private and public higher educational institutions. Dvir et al., (2002) described that transactional leaders refer to active craft in the interior of leaders and subservient where the leader circles specific purposes, shades improve and discriminate rewards which may be usual on objective achievement in diverse situation. Riaz and Haider (2003) narrated that the current research work has focused on the target to determine leadership styles in the universities of Pakistan. In education, in Pakistan, the field is facing significant snags. In this regard, it perceives significance of leadership for professional advancement in education.

Goodwin, Wofford and Whittington (2001) found that the main focus of the leadership and commitment is on the attitude of workers towards occupation performance and organization through association organizational boundary; education institutions have prominent character in the lifting of the socio-economic standards of society. Kent and Chelladurai (2001) asserted that the accessible literature uncovered that transactional leaders are the persons who are observed to inspire employees through affable self-regard. Ryan and Deci (2000) elaborated that the driving force in satisfying and pursuing individuals' needs is motivational behaviour; and strength of individual deeds. According to Bénabou and Tirole (2003), it is vital to inspire and encourage workforces to get success in the fierce and dynamic competition of business in this modern era; for that reason, it is necessary to motivate and encourage workers from all angles. Qayyum and Siddique (2003) cited that each organization may or may not be earning based consists of three types of resources likewise "money, men, machinery". But the vital one is indisputable organizational human resources. Crispin, Michael and Mariri (2004), Steven, Appelbaum and William (2000), asserted that the important effectors for the effectiveness of an organization are employee motivation and leadership and leadership styles effects employee commitment and dedication.

Problem Statement

The Problem addressed in this research are related to prediction of organizational commitment over leadership traits and styles especially transformational and transactional. Commitment has been considered a leading phenomenon that alone is responsible for various individuals' and organisation desired outcomes. Similarly, the motivation has also been placed as a leading predictor toward various desired outcomes like commitment as well as performance along with developing optimistic behaviours.

Research Objectives

1. To evolve a theoretical framework (theory) around relationships between leadership styles and commitment mediated by motivation in HEIs this would serve as a research model for examining hypotheses.
2. To measure commitment as a criterion and motivation as a mediator in connection with leadership style in higher institutions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan in prevailing situation.
3. To attain statistical data about impacts of leadership styles on academician commitment in institutions in diverse magnitudes and capacities in KP universities (higher education institutions).

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provided the core theme of study through background literature. Its emphasis on main phenomenon (leadership) wherein research work was grounded with leadership theories proceeded by the leadership styles. Bass and Avolio (1990) used and adapted which comprises transformational and transactional leadership styles. Mostly, the researchers' uses only two leadership styles (transformational and transactional) that have been used in this study. The second important phenomenon is organizational commitment which was transformed from study of Mayer and Allen (1991). The third important theme of the current study is motivation which is used as mediating variable in current research study. For this purpose, the researcher used/adapted/ followed Edward and Richard's (2001) model of motivation. In this regard, all research variables along with their related attributes were discussed and analyzed in higher education context.

Transactional Leadership

Bass (1997) highlighted that leadership is an unintelligible application as a huge share of the general population is indirectly/ directly, intentionally/unintentionally intricate in influencing others in a leadership role. The initial leadership inquiries had distinctive attention on leaders' persona named as distinctive rumours of the leadership. At that time, it emphasized on leaders determine their attitudes, conduct and behaviours and an era of theories regarding behaviour penetrated contest with attention on leaders' communication with others. Bass (1985) found that transactional leadership generate a base for relations among followers and leaders as per descriptive errands, agreeing prospects, to provide salutation and prizes to get performance which is desired and

craved. Avolio and Bass (1991) explained that transactional leadership denotes the number of agendas about leadership and background that gather the exchange that occurs between employees and the leaders that brings a mutual profit to them. Other researchers described that transactional leadership that focused on security and physical needs of employees. Leadership is found an enthusiastic theme for analysts). Riaz, Akram and Ijaz (2002) illustrated that numerous investigators focused upon the leadership styles in various organizations, and professional settings. In passing, it was seldom observed among teaching faculties of higher education institutions in Pakistan.

Organizational Commitment

Antonakis, Avoird and Sivaramaniam (2003) asserted that the onus, in this regard, falls upon the shoulders of educationists those who are the main pillars of the universities. Conversely, the commitment to a job is vital for the achievement of the aims and goals of an institution. In this linking, focal point in job satisfaction is primarily financial like his/her salary packages and thus the other job-related bonuses, allowances and rewards. Thus, the significance of this topic lies in its association with the employees in one or another way. Irfan et al., (2013) mentioned that academic institutions own their place in the responsibility in the present age in which globalization occurs in a lifetime. Dynamism is said to be done in academic institutions mainly universities have direct relation to its representatives' abilities; workforce procurement to various areas is possible merely by colleges having an abnormal level of educational values and organizational commitment regarding employees especially academicians nationwide. From perspectives of Irfan et al., (2014) and Malik et al., (2010), a very serious establishment is the wellspring of the workforce for purpose of educational development in universities. Universities gradually turn out to be very familiar and acquainted that specialist is the main individual to their attainments and viewpoints of the rise association between labourer and organization as the vital parameter being enhanced.

Motivation

Ryan and Deci (2000) highlighted that this period is of high significance due to encouraging behaviour which occurs in contemporary, its focus is on the future; motivation is a basic tool to regulate the task behaviour of employees. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is critical in employees' lives. Motivation thus remained a significant attribute in maintaining employees' efforts and potential towards desired tasks and contextual performances in attaining desired outcomes through capabilities. Steers, Mowday and Shapiro (2004) pointed out that literature revealed that the employees' needs, supervision, effort, working environment, responsibilities, employee development, feedback, reward and fairness and equity are the main elements and aspects that contribute to motivating employees. Hennessey and Amabile (2005), and Herman and Broeck (2009), that work motivation and values improve one's ability to perform, for reasons are realized as unreliable, acquirable and hierarchical human ethics are enduring and stable, give mien to human desires and offer rules to make conclusions and care one to select amid options. Khaliq (2005) said that as human change inadequacy and insufficiency inspire organizational development. Ronit and Dina (2007) narrated that the stakes of the educational system of any country are only the teachers who play significant role in building the students' personalities. Ahmed et al., (2009) found that many research works have been conducted on the professional development of teachers but not on teacher motivation in developing countries like Pakistan.

Leadership, Motivation & Commitment

This section provides the theoretical relationship among research variables like leadership styles, motivation (intrinsic & extrinsic), and organizational commitment as support over the theoretical framework from where the hypotheses have been developed. According to (Oluseyi and Ayo (2007), and Rudy and Maria (2009), HEIs leaders utilize Vroom's theory to assume that adoptions made through an individual between other action courses are legally connected to mental measures happening with performance, a person energize, directs and sustains his efforts towards attaining particular objectives through the motivation. Walumbwa and Lawler (2003) defined that this style of leadership inspires employee to attain expectable performance levels by serving them to recognize the task errands, know their purposes and make conviction about get-together commitment and desired levels of performance. Yousef (2001), educational leadership is the way to achievement; the motivation behind this study was to distinguish issues confronted by educational leaders to deal with the nature of universities (higher educational institutions) in Pakistan. Teaching is key and conspicuous profession globally, other professions in society have their origins in teaching profession. Rai and Sinha (2005) and Nyengane (2007) narrated that transactional leaders set aims, articulate clear sympathies about how and what leaders get ahead from the employees and rewarded for their efforts along with promise by giving support reproach for care everyone on undertaking; thus, transactional leaders in least popular towards dedication and commitment of the workforces.

Theoretical Support

The present study aimed to examine relationships of different natures among the research variables like predictor, mediators and criterion. In this linking, diverse theoretical background concerning different variables through supported theories has been offered to understand the nature and origin of different research variables from inception to the present period. For this purpose, the Bass Leadership (1985) followed leadership that recommended three leadership styles transformational, transactional and laissez-fair but, later on, only two styles of leadership (transformational & transactional) have gained popularity and momentum and consequently widely researched in different contexts based upon situation and characteristics involved in different phased to provide the proper interest and support.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), the research philosophy describes design of research along with the complete process of research. It talks about observations of scholars about ontology (knowledge existence), epistemology (knowledge communication) and how to acquire knowledge (methodology). The present study philosophy is ontology (empiricism), epistemology (positivism) and methodology (systematic method). The research methodology justifies with provision and applicability of different tools and techniques as per the nature of the research study. The nature of study is quantitative wherein exploratory design was used to execute descriptive and inferential parameters of research used by researchers. The scholar used a survey approach by gathering primary (field data) over questionnaires and secondary (literature review) over already existing data. (Antonis, 2003) found that many researchers suggested that survey is active tool for data collection about aspects (primary & secondary). The questionnaire method is most normally utilized tool for observing the views and opinions of respondents under study for specific research.

Boyd (1977) stated that sampling is typical practice utilized by researchers to make inferences around an extensive gathering of the population on the premise of a small portion of the total population. For instance, articulation in newspaper is consequence of readings wherein views of individuals on a similar substance are anticipated by assembling the feelings from the pair of selected individuals. There are mostly two approaches used for data collection comprises a secondary collection of data and primary data collection. Both the procedures are used in each research study grounded upon the nature of the study and other requirements of research that guide the researcher to use most sophisticated tools and techniques to conduct the study, chase objectives and conclude. Since science is strategy of means to cope with whole experimental domain. To express the suggestions in form of 'if-then', the following is method of investigation that empowers scholars to seek after research. In this regard, two sorts of inquiries regarding the investigation may be brought up in research. Among them, one identifies with "tools and techniques" of demonstrating the information about the area under study. Alternate outfits the routines for ordering them intelligently.

Mediation Analysis

The variable is measured as a mediator when it disturbs the relationship between variables (dependent & independent). To what extent the relationship is affected is based on decisions regarding the mediation (full mediation, partial mediation and no mediation). In previous studies, there were two mediation processes were used among which one is Barren and Kanny (1986) and second Hayes mediation (2007).

Figure 1 Mediation Model

FINDINGS OF STUDY

The findings are the main section, which shows the primary contribution of scholars concerning studies on research. In this section, the decisions were made regarding the rejection and acceptance of the hypotheses of the study. In the mediation model, intrinsic motivation was used as mediating variable in linking transactional style and organizational commitment. The mediation was aimed to check that either intrinsic motivation strengthens or disconnects the association between organizational commitment and transactional style. For this purpose, Hayes's (2008) mediation procedure was used. The mediation offers information that whether

motivation is playing any significant role in connecting the independent and the dependent variables or not and which is the most significant variable among the independent and mediator in connection with the dependent variable.

H1: Role of Intrinsic Motivation In-between Transactional & Commitment

Table 1 Model Summary (Step-a)

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5003	.2503	.4200	157.2269	1.0000	471.0000	.0000

Table 2 Coefficients of Regression(Step-a)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.7009	.2213	12.2049	.0000	2.2660	3.1357
Transactional Leadership	.5706	.0455	12.5390	.0000	.4812	.6600

Predicting Variable: Transactional Leadership

Criterion Variable: Intrinsic Motivation

Table 3 Model Summary (Steps: b & c)

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6503	.4229	.3014	172.2038	2.0000	470.0000	.0000

Table 4 Coefficients of Regression (b & c)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.3398	.2151	6.2294	.0000	.9172	1.7624
Transactional Leadership	.6380	.0445	14.3295	.0000	.5505	.7254
Intrinsic Motivation	.1188	.0390	3.0425	.0025	.0421	.1955

Predicting Variable: Transactional Leadership; Mediating: Intrinsic Mediator; Criterion: Commitment

Table 5 Model Summary (Step-c)

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6415	.4115	.3067	329.3771	1.0000	471.0000	.0000

Table 6 Coefficients of Regression (Step-c)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.6605	.1891	8.7813	.0000	1.2890	2.0321
Transactional Leadership	.7057	.0389	18.1487	.0000	.6293	.7821

Predicting Variable: Transactional Leadership

Criterion Variable: Organizational Commitment

Table 7 Normal Theory Test (Sobel Test)

Effect	Se	Z	p
.3122	.0222	5.6877	.0000

In mediation model, intrinsic motivation was used as mediator in linking amid commitment and transactional. Hayes Process Model (2008) was used to mediation effect check, mediation process contains four steps including "path a, b, c and c'". In first model (path a) (indirect effect) shows 25% change in intrinsic motivation (criterion variable) is in line for predicting variable (transactional style). The transactional leadership shows a significant and positive impact with (β - 0.57 while p- .000). Also, the second mediation step (path b & c) shows 42% change/variation in a variable (dependent) (commitment) because of transactional leadership and intrinsic motivation. Transactional leadership and intrinsic motivation show a significant impact on organizational commitment with (β - 0.63 while p- .000) and (β - 0.24 while p- .025) respectively.

Likewise, the fourth step of mediation offer path (c) by showing 41% change in organizational commitment (criterion variable) as of predictor (transactional leadership) and shows impact (statistically significant) of transactional on organizational commitment (β - 0.70 & p- .000). For deciding the mediation about all four paths, usually, scholars used p-value significance which is prerequisite for mediation procedure. But in the current

model of mediation as all paths are significant, so the mediation decision will be taken on the value of the coefficient. It is noted that the association between transactional style and commitment is partially mediated by intrinsic motivation as per results from the mediation procedure. As the coefficient value declines from (.70) to (.63) and the link residues significant amid transactional style and organizational commitment after arriving at mediator (intrinsic motivation) (0.11) and thus mediation is confirmed.

Thus, it is decided that second mediation model is partial mediation. Therefore, the mediation first model confirms that intrinsic motivation (mediator) plays a significant intermediary role in linking organizational commitment and transactional style. The outcomes of first mediation model in the current study confirm the existing research findings where intrinsic motivation showed its positive significance in between organizational commitment and transactional leadership. These outcomes were expected also from the findings of the current study based upon recommendations from the preceding studies. Thus, from the mediation procedure, hypothesis # 4 about mediating effect of the motivation is thus accepted based upon the results obtained through mediation and confirmed by the Sobel test toward intrinsic motivation as a mediator.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to examine the relationship between the research variables under study in the particular context. The relationship among transactional leadership style and motivation, and organization commitment (criterion variable) in, above tables provided outcomes of present research. The researchers are required to make clear the position of their research studies, next to data analysis. In current study, the researcher compared present study findings with existing studies finding to make clear differences and cohesions (position) of the present study. The hypothesis was about mediating role of intrinsic motivation to link the transactional leadership and organizational commitment by using the macro mediation procedure that was assumed from the theoretical framework and confirmed over mediation. The results showed significant information about the possible mediation among research variables and thus based on these results, the hypothesis was accepted and substantiated. The results revealed that the intrinsic motivation mediated the connection between transactional leadership and commitment over the partial mediation.

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